

The influence of shear rate and rest time on the thixotropy of the complex thixotropic suspension of Fe-Al-Mg-MMH/montmorillonite

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We have studied the influence of the measuring conditions on the thixotropy of the complex thixotropic system with the weight ratio of Fe-Al-Mg-MMH-to-montmorillonite (R) being 0.051, especially the effect of the shear rate (D_1) after high-intense shearing and the rest time (t_s) before measuring the viscosity. The influence of D_1 and t_s was found complex, i.e. when $t_s = 0$, the system showed complex thixotropy when D_1 was low (10, 170 s^{-1}), whereas the thixotropic type changed to positive when D_1 was high (340, 511, 1022 s^{-1}). The viscosity decreased with increasing D_1 . In the studied range of t_s (0–2 h), the system changed from complex thixotropy at low D_1 (10, 170 s^{-1}) and positive thixotropy at high D_1 (340, 511, 1022 s^{-1}) all into negative thixotropy with the prolong of t_s . The viscosity decreased with t_s at low shear rate (10, 170 s^{-1}) and increased with t_s at high shear rate (340, 511, 1022 s^{-1}), respectively. The mechanism is discussed.

The thixotropy of the suspension, defined as a reversible decrease in viscosity with shearing time when a fluid flows at a constant shear rate, is one of the most important aspects of rheology for the dispersion. During our recent studies on the thixotropy of the suspension of aluminium magnesium hydroxide (MMH)-Na-montmorillonite (MT), not only the positive thixotropy and negative thixotropy have been found, but also a novel thixotropic phenomenon has been observed: a given system may display, early and later, positive thixotropic character and negative thixotropic character, which was described as 'complex thixotropy'. In this paper, we have examined the complex thixotropic suspension from two main factors: shear rate and rest time, and the mechanism is discussed.

Results and discussion

Influence of the shear rate:

Fig. 1 shows the influence of the shear rate (D_1) on the change of $\eta \sim t$ for the Fe-Al-Mg-MMH-montmorillonite system with $R = 0.051$ after high-intense shearing ($t_s = 0$). From Fig. 1 it may be concluded that the suspension shows complex thixotropic feature while first increase and then decrease of η with increasing of t when $D_1 = 10 s^{-1}$, and the system also shows complex thixotropy when $D_1 = 170 s^{-1}$, whereas the changing degree lessens compared with that of $D_1 = 10 s^{-1}$, which means that the complex degree becomes weaker. The system shows positive thixotropy with the increase of η with t when $D_1 \geq 340 s^{-1}$, but the changing degree is weak. Therefore, in the studied range of D_1 (10–1022

Fig. 1. Change of viscosity at various shear rate for Fe-Al-Mg-MMH/MT suspension; $R = 0.051$, $t_s = 0$ s: D_1 (1) 10, (2) 170, (3) 340, (4) 511, (5) 1022 s^{-1} .

s^{-1}), the system changes from complex thixotropy to positive thixotropy, which means that the shear rate will influence the type of the thixotropy.

Influence of t_s :

Fig. 2 shows the changing tendency of $\eta \sim t$ for the Fe-Al-Mg-MMH/MT with $R = 0.051$ when D_1 is at 10, 341, 1022 s^{-1} , respectively, after the system was high-intense sheared. The system shows complex thixotropy when D_1 is at 10 s^{-1} and $t_s = 0$ s (Fig. 2(A)); and the viscosity decreases with t when t_s is in the range of 20 min to 2 h, which shows negative thixotropy. In addition, the viscosity decreases gradually with t_s . The result of $D_1 = 170 s^{-1}$ is the same with that of $D_1 = 10 s^{-1}$. The system shows positive thixotropy when D_1 is at 341, 1022 s^{-1} (Fig. 2(B)(C)) and $t_s = 0$ s; and the viscosity decreases with t as t_s is in the range of 20 min to 2 h, which behaves as negative thixotropy, whereas the viscosity increases with t_s and the result of $D_1 = 511 s^{-1}$ is the same with that of $D_1 = 341, 1022 s^{-1}$. The viscosity decreases with increasing of D_1 when t_s are the same.

Fig. 2. Change of viscosity on start-up of shear at (A) 10, (B) 341 and (C) 1022 s^{-1} for Fe-Al-Mg-MMH/MT suspension.

At each series of measurements, suspension was sheared at a high intensity for 20 min and held a rest for different time (t_s) before measurement: $R = 0.051$; t_s : (1) 0 s, (2) 20 min, (3) 40 min, (4) 1 h, (5) 2 h.

Thixotropy is one of the most complex rheological phenomena. Up to now, the mechanism of it has not been thoroughly understood. The studies on the negative thixotropy are concerned with polymer solutions and many theories such as aggregation theory, crystal theory and network theory have been proposed², but they can not be used to explain the negative thixotropy of a suspension. The 'shield effect' theory³ may explain the negative thixotropic results of the polymer-solid suspensions, but can not explain the results of MMH/MT suspensions. During studies on the thixotropy of Mg-Al-MMH-montmorillonite suspensions, we proposed the mechanism of 'dispersion particles-steric network-dense floc units', which can explain the thixotropy of MMH-clay suspensions reasonably⁴. In MMH-clay suspensions, MMH particles possess positive charges while clay particles possess negative charges. So, some structures may exist because of electrostatic attraction between the

two kinds of particles. The high-speed stirring may destroy part of the structures among particles and thereby enhance dispersity of the system obviously. During settling or under low shear rate, the destroyed structures may recover through the following three forms. First, the two kinds of particles approach each other to form the steric continuous network structures over the whole system, viscosity of the system will increase gradually with t , then the suspension will show positive thixotropy. Second, the two kinds of particles may directly form discrete dense floc units, which decrease the viscosity of the system, showing that η decreases with increasing t , i.e. negative thixotropy. Third, the structure formation process in the system may be divided into two stages: first stage, forming steric continuous structures the same as the first form above which shows positive thixotropic character; second stage, forming dense floc units the same as the second form above which shows negative thixotropic character. On the whole, the recovery of structure is carried out through the form of 'dispersed particles-steric network structure - dense floc units', so the system will show complex thixotropy. When particle coagulation is heavier, the systems may display negative thixotropy. When the coagulation is weaker, the systems may display complex thixotropy. When existing in non-coagulation or steric network structure, they may display positive thixotropy.

The structure will be destroyed when the system is high-speed sheared, then the particles are in a state of highly dispersed. And the structure will restore gradually at the low shear rate, D_1 will influence the recovery process so as to affect the thixotropic type. The recovery of the structure is carried out through the form of 'dispersed particles-steric network structure - dense floc units' when D_1 is relatively low ($10-170 s^{-1}$), which shows complex thixotropy. When D_1 is relatively high ($341-1022 s^{-1}$), the high-speed shear rate will hamper the formation of the dense floc units, hence the recovery of the structure is kept at the period of steric network structure, then the recovery of structure is carried out through the form of 'dispersed particles-steric network structure', which behaves as positive thixotropy.

In addition, it can be concluded from Fig. 1 that the viscosity decreases gradually with increasing of D_1 , the reason is that the higher the shear rate is, the weaker the strength of steric network structure, hence the lower the viscosity is.

The influence of t_s on the viscosity is complex, the possible reason is that the system studied was complex thixotropic system, hence the recovery process is through the form of 'dispersed particles-steric network structure - dense floc units'. Then when rested for some time after high-speed shearing ($t_s \geq 20$ min), the recovery process is at the period of formation of dense floc units, then the

particles exist in a state of densed floc units, and there are interactions among the floc units to form the steric structure⁵. When D_1 is low (10, 170 s^{-1}), the low shear rate can not destroy the structure of the densed floc units, but can destroy the structure between the floc units, hence the viscosity decreases gradually with the time, which behaves as negative thixotropy. And longer the t_s is, the higher is the densed degree of the floc units, and therefore, the viscosity decreases with t_s . Whereas when D_1 is high (340, 511, 1022 s^{-1}), the high shear rate can destroy not only the structure of the densed floc units but also part of the structure between the floc units, and as a result the whole structural strength decreases, hence the viscosity decreases with the time, which shows negative thixotropy. And longer the t_s is, the higher is the densed degree of the floc units, and therefore, the stronger the residual structure is under the high-speed shearing, as a result the viscosity increased with t_s . When t_s is the same, the larger the D_1 is, hence the more heavily the structure of the densed floc units and the structure between the floc units are destroyed, and lower the residual structure is, the lower is the viscosity. More reasonable explanation should be discussed further.

Experimental

Fe-Al-Mg-MMH sol used was synthesized by co-precipitation method. To a mixed solution of $FeCl_3$, $AlCl_3$ and $MgCl_2$ (molar ratio of 2 : 2 : 9), diluted ammonia-water (5 : 1 v/v) was slowly added and the resulting sample was washed with deionized water. The sample was peptized at about 80° in an oven for about 24 h to convert it into MMH sol. TEM analysis using a JEM-100cxII transmission electron microscope showed that the sol particles to be hexagonal platelets. Average diameter measured with Zetasizer 3000 was 200.8 nm. Powder XRD pattern obtained using a D/max-rA model showed the MMH to have a well crystallized hydroxalate-type structure.

Montmorillonite suspension :

Montmorillonite (commercial Ca-montmorillonite) was mixed with Na_2CO_3 (weight ratio of Na_2CO_3 : clay being 0.05) and suspended in distilled water by stirring for 20 min using a high-speed mixer (Model GJ-1, Jiangyin Second

Electrical Machinery Plant), and then decanted for 20 min. Thus Ca-montmorillonite changed to Na-montmorillonite.

All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Methods :

The thixotropy was obtained by measuring the gradual recovery change of viscosity as a function of rest time after vigorously stirring with reference to experiments described earlier^{3,6}. And the increase of η and t means positive thixotropy, while the decrease of η with increasing of t means negative thixotropy. First increase and then decrease of η with increasing of t means complex thixotropy. Because the measuring conditions will influence the process of the recovery, the system will show different thixotropic type when the measuring condition and the method are changed⁵. Hence we can understand the rheological regularity and the interaction among the particles by studying the influence of the measuring conditions on the thixotropy. Our previous studies⁵ show that the Fe-Al-Mg-MMH-montmorillonite suspensions behave as complex thixotropy when the weight ratio of MMH to montmorillonite (R) is 0.051, and in this paper the influence of the shear rate and rest time on the thixotropy of the complex thixotropic system was studied.

pH of the suspensions was controlled to be 9.6 ± 0.2 , all the montmorillonite contents in the Fe-Al-Mg-MMH-montmorillonite suspensions were 3% by weight.

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